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Further Explorations in the Southern Fringe of the Ghaggar Plains, District Bhiwani, Haryana

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Abstract

This paper is a preliminary report of the second season (March-April 2012) of the village-to-village survey in the southern fringe of the Ghaggar Plains partly in the Charkhi-Dadri Tehsil of Bhiwani District, Haryana. A total of 75 sites have been documented and explored. By focusing on this area we hope to better understand the issues such as the relationship between the Ganeshwar-Jodhpura culture complex of northern Rajasthan and the Harappan Civilization; and also the expansion of the Harappan Civilization in the southwestern fringe region of the Ghaggar Plains; and the general information about the archaeological sites in the region.

Introduction

In continuation of the explorations carried out by Dangi and Kumar in 2011, this year i.e. 2012, we not only extended our explorations to the area adjacent to that of the previous year, but also conducted an intensive village-to-village survey in the southern fringe of the Ghaggar Plains. This was undertaken with the aim of studying the cultural sequence in the arid zone; to trace the expansion of the Ganeshwar-Jodhpura culture complex; and view its relationship with the Harappans. This area is important to help understand the mode of interaction between the inhabitants of the Harappan culture and the Ganeshwar-Jodhpura culture. Topography, drainage system, fauna, flora, mineral resources and methodology have been discussed in detail in the previous report (Dangi and Kumar 2013).

Previously, this area was explored by Suraj Bhan (1972) and Yasvir Singh (1991) as a part of their Ph.D. and M.Phil research work, respectively and later some sites reported by these scholars were listed by Possehl (1999) and Manmohan Kumar (2009). However, thus far, no site has yet been excavated in the area under study. Against this background, we carried out a village-to-village survey in Dadri Block-2 of Bhiwani District, Haryana.

Discussion

The explorations carried out in the region using the village-to-village survey method yielded 75 sites ranging from Early Harappan to the Medieval period (Tables 1-2). Sothi-Siswal is a regional variant of the Early Harappan culture in the upper and middle Ghaggar Basin. Most of the Sothi-Siswal pottery was usually thrown on a slow wheel; the rim and neck portions were finished by smoothening with rotation; the body portion was finished without rotation as striations and finger impressions from smoothening and scraping have been observed on the surface in an irregular way. Usually the wall of the pot by nature has an uneven thickness. Ring base and loop-handled pots are quite common. Kalibangan Fabric B and D are rare. Although incised decoration sherds are present, typologically these are akin to Ganeshwar-Jodhpura pottery.

Of eight Mature Harappan sites, only a few classical Harappan shapes viz. perforated jar, dish-on-stand vases, were recovered from the surface. Other antiquities collected from the site include beads of agate, faience, steatite, and long tubular terracotta beads (imitation of long barrel shaped carnelian beads) (Fig. 2). Chert blades are rare in this region; not even a single blade/flake/core, etc. was recovered during the explorations. Manheru and Mitathal are the two excavated sites in the vicinity of the study area but only a few chert blades were recovered from Mitathal (Suraj Bhan 1975: Plate XIX.A; Kumar *et al.* 2012: Figs. 25.35).

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Table 1: Explored sites with previous work and cultural sequence (Fig. 1)

Sr. No	Site	Longitude	Latitude	Area (ha)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
1	Achina-1	28 ° 40' 47.0"	76 ° 22' 02.8"	1.5	Yasvir 1991: 9	EH, MH, LH, Hist. (Ganeshwar-Jodhpura pottery recovered)
2	Achina-2	28 ° 39' 39.9"	76 ° 21' 57.3"	1	Yasvir 1991: 9	LH, Hist, Med.
3	Ajitpura	28 ° 43' 15.7"	76 ° 10' 30.8"	3	New Site	LH, Hist, Med.
4	Bhageshwari	28 ° 41' 05.1"	76 ° 20' 11.8"	1	Yasvir 1991:10	LH.
5	Bhagvi	28 ° 36' 30.7"	76 ° 23' 28.0"	2	New	LH., Burial
6	Bigowa	28 ° 39' 45.8"	76 ° 25' 01.1"	3	New Site	Hist., Med.
7	Bir Smaspur	28 ° 36' 34.1"	76 ° 19' 36.8"	1	New Site	Hist.
8	Dhani Phaugat	28 ° 35' 03.3"	76 ° 18' 51.1"	1	Yasvir 1991:10	Med.
9	Ghasola-1	28 ° 33' 21.4"	76 ° 15' 30.5"	4	New Site	Hist.
10	Ghasola-2	28 ° 32' 51.8"	76 ° 15' 39.9"	4	New Site	Hist., Med.
11	Ghasola-3	28 ° 32' 35.6"	76 ° 15' 23.1"	2	New Site	Hist., Med.
12	Gothra-1	28 ° 31' 01.6"	76 ° 18' 34.1"	1	Yasvir 1991:10-11	Hist., Med.
13	Gothra-2	28 ° 31' 17.0"	76 ° 19' 10.0"	2	Yasvir 1991:11	Hist., Med.
14	Gothra-3	28 ° 30' 20.3"	76 ° 19' 34.2"	2	New Site	LH, Med.
15	Hindol	28 ° 42' 26.5"	76 ° 16' 10.0"	1/2	New Site	Med.
16	Imlota	28 ° 37' 59.3"	76 ° 26' 12.3"	1	New Site	Hist., Med.
17	Jhinjar-1	28 ° 39' 21.0"	76 ° 21' 05.1"	5	Suraj Bhan 1975: 125	EH, MH, LH.
18	Jhinjar-2	28 ° 40' 30.7"	76 ° 20' 14.4"	2	New Site	Hist.
19	Kamodh-1	28 ° 38' 51.8"	76 ° 18' 16.5"	1	New Site	Hist.
20	Kamodh-2	28 ° 38' 38.5"	76 ° 17' 07.1"	1	New Site	LH., Hist.
21	Kanheti	28 ° 37' 19.2"	76 ° 24' 10.6"	1/2	New Site	Hist., Med.
22	Kapuri-1	28 ° 34' 07.3"	76 ° 16' 50.1"	1	Yasvir 1991:12	Hist., Med.
23	Kapuri-2/Pahadi	28 ° 33' 28.4"	76 ° 17' 16.9"	5	New Site	Hist., Med.
24	Kheri Sanwal-1	28 ° 33' 22.4"	76 ° 18' 54.0"	1	New Site	Hist., Med.
25	Kheri Sanwal-2	28 ° 32' 38.6"	76 ° 18' 43.5"	2	New Site	Hist., Med.
26	Khetiwas-1	28 ° 37' 23.1"	76 ° 18' 04.9"	1	New Site	Hist., Med.
27	Khetiwas-2	28 ° 37' 26.6"	76 ° 18' 39.9"	1	New Site	Hist.
28	Khetiwas-3	28 ° 39' 07.0"	76 ° 19' 08.5"	2	New Site	MH, LH. (Ganeshwar-Jodhpura pottery was recovered)
29	Khurd Tikan	28 ° 33' 12.9"	76 ° 17' 35.7"	3	New Site	Hist., Med.
30	Kidara	28 ° 39' 10.8"	76 ° 25' 14.3"	5	New Site	Hist., Med.
31	Kolhawas-1	28 ° 40' 51.8"	76 ° 18' 30.2"	2	Yasvir 1991:12	Hist., Med.
32	Kolhawas-2	28 ° 41' 12.3"	76 ° 18' 30.0"	5	Yasvir 1991:13	Hist., Med.
33	Lamba-1	28 ° 41' 00.3"	76 ° 17' 16.2"	4	Yasvir 1991:13	Hist., Med.
34	Lamba-2	28 ° 40' 59.9"	76 ° 17' 44.1"	1/2	New Site	Med.
35	Loharwala-1	28 ° 37' 54.9"	76 ° 21' 18.8"	3	Yasvir 1991:13	Hist., Med.
36	Loharwala-2	28 ° 37' 33.9"	76 ° 20' 11.6"	3	New Site	Hist.
37	Makrana	28 ° 29' 24.6"	76 ° 16' 46.9"	4	Yasvir 1991:14	Hist., Med.
38	Makrani	28 ° 30' 48.0"	76 ° 16' 44.1"	3	Yasvir 1991:14	Hist., Med.
39	Manheru-1	28 ° 42' 28.4"	76 ° 14' 17.9"	1	Thakaran et al. 2010: 128-159	MH, LH. (Ganeshwar-Jodhpura pottery recovered)
40	Manheru-2	28 ° 42' 42.5"	76 ° 14' 19"	1	New Site	MH, LH, Hist.

Sr. No	Site	Longitude	Latitude	Area (ha)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
41	Mauri	28° 31' 49.1"	76° 16' 50.6"	2	New Site	Hist.
42	Mehrana	28° 33' 28.4"	76° 19' 45.3"	2	Yasvir 1991:14	Hist., Med.
43	Mirch-1	28° 38' 29.6"	76° 16' 13.7"	4	Yasvir 1991:15	LH, Hist.
44	Mirch-2	28° 38' 49.3"	76° 15' 37.5"	1	New Site	Hist.
45	Misri	28° 40' 11.5"	76° 17' 22.8"	3	Yasvir 1991:15	MH, LH.
46	Morwala-1	28° 38' 27.5"	76° 22' 52.6"	1	Yasvir 1991:15	EH, LH, Hist., Med.
47	Morwala-2	28° 38' 17.9"	76° 23' 52.3"	1	Yasvir 1991:16	Hist.
48	Nimli	28° 35' 17.5"	76° 25' 06.9"	10	Yasvir 1991:16	Hist., Med.
49	Nimri-1	28° 48' 14.3"	76° 19' 07.2"	2	Yasvir 1991:16	Hist., Med.
50	Nimri-2	28° 47' 40.8"	76° 19' 39.8"	3	New Site	Hist., Med.
51	Patuwas	28° 34' 32.7"	76° 19' 49.7"	1	Yasvir 1991:17	Hist., Med.
52	Phaugat	28° 44' 23.8"	76° 18' 44.4"	2	New Site	Med.
53	Ramnagar	28° 33' 34.5"	76° 16' 43.5"	2	New Site	Hist., Med.
54	Ranila-1	28° 42' 21.9"	76° 20' 44.3"	4	Yasvir 1991:18	Hist., Med.
55	Ranila-2	28° 42' 58.0"	76° 20' 16.2"	2	New Site	EH, MH, LH, (Ganeshwar-Jodhpura recovered)
56	Ranila-3	28° 41' 41.0"	76° 22' 52.6"	2	New Site	Med.
57	Ranila-4	28° 43' 31.1"	76° 21' 04.6"	2	New Site	EH, MH, Hist.
58	Ranila-5	28° 43' 49.8"	76° 22' 23.7"	3	New Site	Hist., Med.
59	Rankoli	28° 46' 15.6"	76° 19' 35.2"	2	Yasvir 1991:18	Hist., Med.
60	Rawhaldi-1	28° 36' 40.8"	76° 17' 53.7"	1/2	New Site	Hist., Med.
61	Rawhaldi-2	28° 38' 03.9"	76° 16' 08.8"	1	New Site	LH., Hist.
62	Sanjarwas	28° 42' 38.2"	76° 18' 48.4"	1	Yasvir 1991:18	Med.
63	Sankror	28° 45' 32.1"	76° 16' 51.6"	3	New Site	Hist., Med.
64	Santor-1	28° 36' 18.7"	76° 24' 25.4"	3	Yasvir 1991:18	Hist., Med.
65	Santor-2	28° 35' 57.8"	76° 24' 45.4"	1/2	Yasvir 1991:19	Med.
66	Santoshpura-1	28° 30' 51.9"	76° 18' 05.9"	2	Yasvir 1991:19	Hist., Med.
67	Santoshpura-2	28° 30' 34.9"	76° 17' 59.0"	6	New Site	Hist.
68	Saunp Kasni-1	28° 40' 24.4"	76° 14' 28.5"	2	Yasvir 1991:19	Hist., Med.
69	Saunp Kasni-2	28° 40' 31.0"	76° 14' 57.1"	1	New Site	Med.
70	Saunp Kasni-3	28° 40' 43.3"	76° 15' 27.4"	2	New Site	LH.
71	Sawrupgarh	28° 36' 31.9"	76° 25' 15.4"	2	Yasvir 1991:19	Hist., Med.
72	Tikan Kalan-1	28° 34' 28.4"	76° 17' 16.8"	1	Yasvir 1991:19	Hist., Med.
73	Tikan Kalan-2	28° 33' 53.6"	76° 17' 46.2"	1/2	Yasvir 1991:19	Hist., Med.
74	Tikan Kalan-3	28° 34' 22.0"	76° 17' 58.2"	1.5	Yasvir 1991:20	Hist., Med.
75	Tikan Kalan-4	28° 33' 40.2"	76° 17' 56.2"	1/2	New Site	Hist.

EH = Early Harappan, MH = Mature Harappan, LH = Late Harappan, Hist = Historical, Med = Medieval.

Fig. 1: Map showing explored and other excavated sites

Table 2: showing number of sites of different periods

Period	No. of Sites
Early Harappan	05
Mature Harappan	08
Late Harappan	17
Historical	57
Medieval	50

At Achina-1, Khetiwas-3, Manheru-1, Ranila-2, Ganeshwar-Jodhpura pottery was found in abundance indicating that Harappans had strong trading relations with the Ganeshwar-Jodhpura inhabitants. Mitathal is the nearest excavated site and each of the sherds was studied by the third author. In the entire ceramic assemblage of Mitathal, the Ganeshwar-Jodhpura pottery was found in limited number. But, as we move south of Mitathal, i.e. in the area under present study, the quantity of Ganeshwar-Jodhpura pottery increases. The ceramic assemblage of Ganeshwar-Jodhpura culture includes bowls, basins and vases (Fig. 3). It is pertinent to note that it is the first time

Fig. 2: Harappan beads recovered during explorations

the Ganeshwar-Jodhpura pottery has been reported from Harappan sites.

Seventeen sites have yielded evidence of Late Harappan culture. The characteristic features of Late Harappan pottery include dish-on-stands with ribbed junction, dish-on-stand with broad and short stands,

Fig. 3: Ganeshwar-Jodhpura culture pottery from various sites of area under present study

Fig. 4: Late Harappan pottery from Ranila-2

vases with projected undercut rims (Fig. 4), jars with wide and narrow mouths, globular vases with flanged rims, beakers with out-turned rims and flasks treated with fine red slip. Of the 17 Late Harappan sites, 10 seem to have been occupied for the first time. Seven Mature Harappan sites were occupied by the Late Harappan people. It appears that the Mature Harappan culture gradually transformed into the Late Harappan, as noted at Mitathal (Kumar *et al.* 2012: 148-179).

Noteworthy finds include a spearhead and copper bangles of Copper Hoard's tool tradition culture, from Khetiwas-3 (Figs. 5-6). Copper tools reported from Mitathal, Bhiwani, and Narnaund are typologically similar to the Copper Hoard tools reported from the Ganga Basin and Rajasthan. These are generally associated with Ochre Coloured Pottery (OCP). This area was occupied by the Late Harappans in the second millennium BCE. At Mitathal a broken harpoon was recovered from the stratigraphic context (Suraj Bhan 1971: 2). The OCP type pottery reported

Fig. 5: Copper spear head from Khetiwas-3 (Copper Hoard tools traditions)

Fig. 6: Copper Bangles from Khetiwas-3

from the Ganga-Yamuna *doab* has a lot of similarity with the Late Harappan pottery of the Ghaggar Basin. The occurrence of Copper Hoards and typological similarities with the OCP and Late Harappan pottery of the Ghaggar Basin indicate that the OCP of the Ganga-Yamuna *doab* has its antecedents in the Late Harappan pottery of the Ghaggar Basin. Some copper bangles were also recovered during the exploration from Khetiwas-3.

Fifty-seven historical sites were explored. This indicates that after 600 BCE the area was densely populated as compared to the Proto-historic period. Common shapes of historical pottery were represented by bowls with incurved rims, carrinated cooking *handis*, vases, spouted vases, basins, lids, and incense burners. Pottery of the Kushana and Gupta periods displays minimum painting as compared to the pottery of the Rangmahal phase. A few sherds decorated with the peacock motif have been recovered (Fig. 7). Naurangabad (Senger 2005: 191-195) and Kokhrakakot (Kumar 1996) were regional centers during the Historical period. Both sites are located very near the study area. Two copper coins in fairly good condition representing the Kushana

Fig. 7: Historical Pottery from Nimili

Fig. 8: Medieval coins from Bigowa

ruler Vasudeva-I were recovered from the Santore-1. At Khokhrakot and Naurangabad, Kushana mints have been reported (Saraswati 1979; Kumar 1996: 95-114). In the adjoining area a number of sites have yielded Kushana coins (Singh, Surender 1989:20, Pl. III, Dangi 2006). A fragmentary inscription of the Kushana period was reported from Village Chirya (IAR 1978-79: 79); this inscription was discussed

in the previous report (Dangi and Kumar 2013); apart from this two Kushana inscriptions have been reported from Khokhrakot (Kumar 1996: 95-114). Recovery of Kushana coins and inscriptions indicates that the area under present study was important during the this period.

Fifty medieval sites were documented during the survey. The main shapes include sharp edged bowls, vases, and pots. During the exploration, six medieval coins were found from Bigowa. All these belong to the Sultanate period. These are described in Table 3 (Fig. 8). Till today, no scholar has paid attention to the medieval coins of Haryana or adjoining regions.

Conclusion

As a result of explorations in the southern fringe of the Ghaggar Plains, 134 sites have been explored and studied. Of these 59 sites were covered in the first preliminary survey (Dangi and Kumar 2011). The geographical area under the present study is marked by a sluggish transition to the Thar Desert. The topography is characterized by aeolian deposits of various shapes and thicknesses overlying Pleistocene alluvium. Most of the study area is plain except for some detached outliers of the Aravalli Range. There is no perennial or seasonal source of water other than the monsoon showers; the land is also not so fertile; less availability of water and less fertile land can be viewed as hurdles to establish human settlements. However, Harappans preferred this region to establish their settlements; it seems that Early/Mature/Late Harappans preferred to occupy this area to establish their out-posts to extract copper from the Khetri mines through Ganeshwar-Jodhpura culture people and to supply sandstone objects viz. grinding stones, saddle querns, pestles etc., from the Kaliana Hills. The sandstone of Kaliana Hills has a sugary texture and is red-pink to pinkish grey in colour and is criss-crossed with thin hematite and quartz filled fractures. These are the unique characteristic features of stone objects from the Kaliana Hills (Law 2011: 119). So it is easy to identify Kaliana sandstone at any site. A number of grinding stones, saddle querns, pestles, etc. of Kaliana sandstone have been reported from Harappa (Law 2011: 120, Figure 5.24; C and D), which is around 300 km away. One major aim of the present study was to identify Harappan workshops around the Kaliana Hills; unfortunately the authors were unable to locate or identify them around the Kaliana Hills, perhaps owing to modern human

Table 3: Medieval coins

Sr. No.	Site	Ruler	Metal	Size, thickness and Shape	Weight	Obverse	Reverse
1	Bigowa	Firuz Shah	Billon	17.82 mm; 4.13 mm; Circular	8.76 g	<i>Firuz shah sultani duribat bi-hadrat dehli</i>	<i>Al-khalifa abu 'abd allah khulidat khilafatuhu</i>
2	Bigowa	Firuz Shah	Billon	17.69 mm; 4.31 mm; circular	8.76 g	<i>Firuz shah sultani duribat bi-hadrat dehli</i>	<i>Al-khalifa abu 'abd allah khulidat khilafatuhu</i>
3	Bigowa	Firuz Shah	Billon	16.69 mm; 4.66 mm; circular	8.73 g	<i>Firuz shah sultani duribat bi-hadrat dehli</i>	<i>Al-khalifa abu 'abd allah khulidat khilafatuhu</i>
4	Bigowa	Fath Khan S/o Firuz Shah.	Billon	18.31 mm; 4.18 mm; circular	8.66 g	<i>Fathkhan firuz shah jall allah zillalahu jalalahu</i>	<i>Fi-zaman al-imam amir al-muminin abi abd allah khulidat khilafatuhu.</i>
5	Bigowa	Fath Khan S/o Firuz Shah.	Billon	17.58 mm; 4.40 mm; circular	9.04 g	<i>Fathkhan firuz shah jall allah zillalahu jalalahu</i>	<i>Fi-zaman al-imam amir al-muminin abi abd allah khulidat khilafatuhu.</i>
6	Bigowa	Firuz Shah.	Silver	21.83 mm, 3.32 mm, circular	11.22 g	<i>Al-sultan al-a'zam abu'l muzaffar mahmud shah muhammad shah firuz shah sultani</i>	<i>Fi-zaman al-imam amir al-mu'minin khulidat khilafatuhu</i>

activities. In the Ghaggar Plains, the Tosham Hills was the only source of tin and copper (Murao *et al.* 2008). Availability of copper, tin and sandstone makes this area of significance during the proto-historic period.

Most Harappan sites in the study region have an area of two or three hectares. The size of Jhinjar-1 (5 hectares) and the material culture recovered from the surface indicates that it was a regional center in the southern fringe of the Ghaggar Plains and played an important role in controlling trade during the Harappan period.

There are two domains of the Late Harappan culture in the Ghaggar Basin and the areas of both were delineated with the help of explorations, distribution maps and typological studies of the pottery (Dangi 2010: 388; map 6.1; appendix-1). The study area falls in Mitathal-IIIB domain. Discovery of a typical Copper Hoard tradition spear head from Khetiwas-3 and generic similarity in Ochre Coloured Pottery (OCP) and Late Harappan pottery of the Ghaggar Plains indicates that Late Harappans, OCP and Copper Hoards culture was the last stage of the Harappan Civilization.

Iron ore is reported from Kaliana Hills, which is located in the study area (Haryana District Gazetteers,

Bhiwani 1982: 15). Inhabitants of the Painted Grey Ware culture were first in the Ghaggar Plains, who knew iron smelting technology. Not even a single PGW site is located in the vicinity of iron sources. Although iron smelting activities were noticed at a number of sites, all these sites belonged to the later periods.

During the historical period, the area in this study played an important role. Urban settlements like Naurangabad and Khokhrakot were sustained because of the rural or peripheral sites which provided their surplus agricultural produce to these centers. At Naurangabad, coins of the Yaudheyas, Indo-Greeks and Kushanas indicate that it was a regional and administrative center during the 2nd century BCE to 3-4th century A.D. At some historical sites around Kaliana Hills iron smelting evidence has been recorded during the exploration, indicating that these small sites had a very important role in trade and commerce. Discovery of silver and copper coins of the Sultanate and Mughal period indicate that this region was equally important during the Medieval period.

The researchers conducted explorations following the village-to-village survey method and recorded

sites with the help of GPS. This helped to update and correct the earlier survey data; work carried out by the earlier scholars (Bhan 1975; Joshi *et al.* 1984; Yasvir 1991; Possehl 1999; Kumar 2009, etc.) who had noted sites mentioning just the latitude and longitude and only in a few places seconds were mentioned. The absence of seconds or minutes with a decimal place, means that data is not complete and if we plot the site on the map without the seconds with decimal the site will vary from several hundred meters to several kilometres from its original location and with incomplete data it not possible to study micro settlement pattern in relation to geographical setting. Recently, some scholars surveyed other parts of Haryana addressing this problem (Dangi 2007, 2009a, 2009b, 2010, 2011; Dangi and Kumar 2013; Singh *et al.* 2010 and 2011). When our study is combined with this work, future researchers shall have a comprehensive and exact database.

Most of the archaeological sites already documented have either been converted into agriculture fields or had the soil removed for some other development purpose. The situation is very grim indeed because in a few years it will be very difficult for archaeologists to locate any site for excavation. Even today it is very hard to spot an intact mound.

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